

Making your own Mannequins

Sarah Clayton

Australian War Memorial

The Australian War Memorial (AWM) has adapted a system developed by Denis Larouche (1995) for constructing Ethafoam mannequins. After much research the AWM found there were no mannequins on the market that would meet our out needs and the adapted Larouche mannequins are sturdy enough to support military uniforms with full kits, are light weight, and manufactured to fit each individual uniform.

The Australian War Memorial has developed a manual designed to be a step-by-step guide for constructing intersecting silhouette mannequins from 100mm planks of Ethafoam. The manual's aim is to fill in the gaps that could not be covered in detail in Larouche's 1995 article. The AWM has also adapted and improvised methods for leg supports, arms, and neck finishes. You will, no doubt, develop many more variations for each new situation that arises.

The Mannequin Manual is available on CD from the Australian War Memorial.

Further reading

Drummond, G., 1997, The Arbortech Mini-carver: An Australian invention – the perfect tool for carving Ethafoam. *AICCM National Newsletter*, no 65, December, 1997.

Kienitz, G., 1996, Observations on the construction of intersecting silhouette mannequins for use with women's fashionable clothing. *Textile Conservation Newsletter*, Ottawa, no. 31, fall, 1996.

Larouche, D. 1995, Intersecting silhouette mannequins. *Textile Conservation Newsletter*, Ottawa, Spring Supplement, 1995.

Woodruff, S, 1999, In search of the ideal military mannequin. *Textile conservation Newsletter*, Ottawa, no 36, 1999.